

A NOTE ON POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION OF GALLIC ACID

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Gallic acid is one of the important constituents which offer colour and in part, the acid nature to the sugarcane juices ; it is also employed as an analytical reagent (Datta, this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 687 ; Charlot, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1948, 1, 218). For a clear understanding of the exact contribution or/ and the role of gallic acid in the above process, the knowledge of the dissociation constant K of an apparently primary reaction

TABLE I

Determination of the dissociation constant of gallic acid.

NaOH	t_{H^+}	Conc. of free gallic acid $\times 10^4$.	α .	$[\text{HA}] \times 10^3$.	$[\text{A}^-] \times 10^3$.	$K \times 10^5$.
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
0 c.c.	3.40	21.30	0.019	20.95	0.35	0.67
1	3.68	19.59	0.011	19.37	1.63	1.72
2	3.83	17.93	0.008	17.78	2.93	2.44
3	4.00	16.29	0.006	16.18	4.22	2.61
4	4.10	14.74	0.005	14.67	5.48	2.96
5	4.22	13.21	0.005	13.15	6.73	3.09
6	4.32	11.72	0.004	11.67	7.95	4.11
7	4.43	10.26	0.004	10.23	9.85	3.58
8	4.53	8.86	0.003	8.83	10.29	3.44
9	4.64	7.48	0.003	7.46	11.42	3.51
10	4.78	6.14	0.003	6.13	12.34	3.39
11	4.91	4.82	0.003	4.81	13.59	3.48
12	5.10	3.55	0.002	3.54	14.64	3.28
13	5.35	2.30	0.002	2.30	15.67	3.05
14	5.74	1.10	0.002	1.10	16.69	2.77
15	6.70		0.002			
16	7.45					
17	7.70					
18	7.90					
19	8.10					
20	8.18					

is of importance, on which no data exist in the literature. The present note reports the determination of K by potentiometric titration method. Gallic acid of B.D.H. quality was recrystallised in water several times and later dried at 160° , till the product gave a constant m.p. (252°). A known volume of gallic acid solution was titrated against standard NaOH solution in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The B.M.F. or the H^+ -concentration at every stage of titration was measured by the combination of Beckman's glass and calomel electrodes (accuracy = 0.05 of a p_H unit).

Table I records a typical series of results obtained during titration of 70 c.c. of 0.0213*M* of gallic acid against 0.1*N*-NaOH at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$; of these, the data in columns 1 and 2 are shown graphically by curve 1 in Fig. 1; curve 2 represents the data for 60 c.c. of the acid solution. These curves indicate a remarkably clear inflexion at the end-point of the titration. The results in column 3 represent the concentration of the acid minus that which was supposed to be converted into the salt. In the solution phase, a part of this free acid dissociates and contributes to the hydrogen-ion concentration of the solution (*vide supra*). The observed p_H is therefore a measure of the amount of free acid dissociated into H^+ and A^- . α , the degree of dissociation, is obtained by dividing the H^+ -concentration by the concentration of the free acid (column 4); the amount of the undissociated acid is shown in column 5. The data in column 6 refer to the concentration of the anion $[A^-]$, given by the sum of the anion produced by dissociation

FIG. 1

of the free acid and that obtained by sodium salt. The results in the last column provide the values of $K = [H^+][A^-]/[HA]$.

An examination of the data in the last column indicates that K varies appreciably in the beginning and at the end-point of the titration. In the middle portion of the titration, the system was expected to be stable especially on account of the buffer action due to the existence of corresponding though not equal (roughly equivalent, only at half-neutralisation point) quantities of acid and the salt. In accord with this, over a considerable range of titration (7-11 c.c. of NaOH, column 1, Table I), the value of K was within 3.39 to 3.58×10^{-2} ; an average of these gave a value of 3.48×10^{-2} for K , in

agreement with the pK value computed from the observed p_H (4.49 and 4.46, curves 1 and 2, Fig. 1) at half-neutralisation point.

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